

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Sensory attributes, physico-chemical and cooking quality of pasta formulated with durum wheat semolina and refined wheat flour

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ABSTRACT

Italian-style pasta is rarely made with soft wheat flour since it is of inferior quality than durum wheat. The market is gradually moving away from utilizing durum wheat to manufacture pasta as durum wheat is more expensive than other varieties of wheat. In this study, conventional ingredients i.e. Durum Wheat Semolina (DWS) and Refined Wheat flour (RWF) were used for preparation of pasta in alone and in-combination in different ratio & also examined for their effect on the pasta quality. Initially conventional pasta was prepared by using DWS (100%) alone which was altered simultaneously with different ratio of RWF i.e. 90:10, 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40%. The best resulted ratio was further examined for various quality parameters. In order of organoleptic aspects, sensory quality of formulated Pasta samples were evaluated on the basis of 9-point hedonic scale. It was observed that Pasta sample prepared with DWS: RWF (70:30) ratio scored more acceptability from semi-trained panellist in comparison to other treatments. This ratio was further tested for various physico-chemical properties & cooking quality parameters. On the basis of results obtained, it might assumed that pasta sample prepared with DWS: RWF might be an economical approached and also have good stability while processing.

Keywords: Conventional ingredients, durum wheat semolina, pasta, refined wheat flour, sensory analysis

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INTRODUCTION

Pasta is an ancestral Italian food, conventionally manufactured from durum wheat. That is well-known around the world for its variety, extremely acceptable sensory traits, affordable cost, outstanding shelf stability, and simplicity of preparation (Kamble et al., 2019). Due to specific protein profile, durum wheat has been identified as the best grain to use when producing pasta since it results in a dough with high functionality and dough-retaining qualities (Sharma et al., 2021). Dried pasta is a basic food made from wheat. It is the second most popular food in the world considering low price, nutritional value, diversity, ease of preparation and preservation, long shelf life, and appealing sensory qualities. Pasta is typically made through a sequence of basic actions including hydration, mixing, extrusion or lamination, drying, and packaging. Conventionally without the use of colouring or

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preservatives, durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum*, subsp. *durum*) semolina and water (30 g/100 g) are used to make the dough for pasta production. Durum wheat semolina (DWS) is the preferred raw material for creating pasta for centuries. DWS is unique in characteristics and have high protein content (10.9–13.5%), which results in good functionality and the suitable dough structure qualities. Despite having a high starch digestibility, a strong gluten content, and low levels of vitamins, fibre, and beneficial components, Durum wheat semolina is widely utilised (Romano et al., 2021).

From decade's best pasta constituents are made from durum wheat, although durum wheat is more expensive than other types of wheat, the market is gradually moving away from using durum wheat to make pasta. Due to distinctive colour, flavour, and cooking qualities, durum wheat (*Triticum durum*) is the cereal of choice for making pasta (Feillet and Dexter, 1996). However, many pasta or spaghetti products are also made from bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) due to its cost and availability (Fuad and Prabhasankar, 2010). Due to lower quality in comparison to durum wheat, soft wheat flour is rarely utilised to make Italian-style pasta. Studies have revealed that product created from blends of durum and soft wheat containing up to 25% soft wheat are entirely acceptable and legal. To get a high-quality product, however, it becomes necessary to apply extra chemicals or adopt some amendments in conventional ingredients, with better processing techniques. With an annual production of over 2.5 million tonnes, India is a significant producer of durum wheat and has the ability to export this grain to international markets. Due to the exceptional rheological qualities of the batter, as well as the excellent colour, cooking quality, and the consumer acceptance of the product, durum semolina is typically used to make the best pasta products (Coz-Bolaños et al., 2018; Dexter and Matsuo, 1979; Fuad and Prabhasankar, 2010).

Currently despite having a lot of protein and carotenoids, and other qualities, durum wheat is less utilized in developing country for the preparation of basic pasta so a variety of wheat flour can be utilised with DWS which enhance the texture, flavour, and colour as well as cooking qualities of conventional pasta. The information above in some way illustrates the significance of the essential elements needed to make pasta, which determine the quality of the finished product. According to Bustos et al., the durum wheat as well as wheat flour from *Triticum durum* and *Triticum aestivum* can be used to make pasta (Bustos et al., 2011). In present study an attempt was made to prepare a most suitable combination of conventional pasta with DWS and RWF, in terms of consumer acceptance (sensory evaluation) as well as its quality parameters such as physical properties (swelling capacity, gluten content and bulk density), chemical properties (carbohydrate, protein, fat, moisture, ash and energy value) and cooking quality parameters were also studied.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The details of materials and methodologies were described under following sections to evaluate the sensory analysis of pasta prepared with Durum Wheat Semolina (DWS) alone and in different combination of Refined Wheat Flour (RWF) and also studied physico-chemical properties as well as cooking quality parameters of best selected combination of DWS and RWF.

Raw materials

In present study, Durum Wheat Semolina (DWS) and Refined Wheat Flour (RWF) were used as raw materials with water. For pasta preparation, good quality commercially available durum wheat semolina and refined wheat flour were purchased from local market.

Experimental design

In present study, an attempt was made to prepared a good quality pasta by using DWS (100%) alone and in-combination with different concentrations/ ratio of Durum Wheat Semolina (DWS) and Refined Wheat Flour (RWF) *i.e.*, DWS: RWF at 90:10%,

80:20%, 70:30%, and 60:40% with the help of water (32 to 34%) and maintain the weight proportion of control pasta. The selection of raw materials for pasta preparation is a very critical part out of the entire process as their composition as well as physical properties can directly affect the Physico-chemical properties of end product (Nilusha et al., 2019). Best combination of pasta (DWS: RWF) among the treatments/tested groups were further evaluated for its physico-chemical characteristics and cooking quality parameters.

Preparation of Pasta Samples

Initially raw materials i.e. DWS & RWF flours and water was mixed in pasta mixer-extruder machine (Model: Dolly La Monferrina, Italy) followed by kneading in to a dough. Required amount of water was added to an amount to keep the moisture content around 32-34% in mixture. Mixing and kneading was done for an optimum time of 20-30 min till it produces homogeneous dough. A sharp blade cutter is now fix in front of the die in extrusion machine and the speed of the sharp blade cutter was adjusted as per requirement which cut the dough in the desired shape of Pasta. The pasta samples were dried in cabinet drier at around 55°C for 90-120 min. Followed by cooling at ambient room temperature for around 20-30min & then packed in commercially available zip poly bags pouches (Singh et al., 2004).

Quality characteristics

The prepared Pasta samples and blend flour of best selected ratio of developed pasta (DWS: RWF) was tested for various quality parameters.

Sensory evaluation of developed Pasta

Sensory analysis of cooked Pasta was carried out by using 9 point hedonic scales (Ranganna, 1986) by semi- trained panel of 10 members. Various parameters like colours, flavour, texture, taste and overall acceptability were taken for analysis and average of these parameters was recorded.

Physical parameters

The Physical properties such as bulk density, swelling capacity and gluten content of developed Pasta blend flours were conducted.

Bulk Density of Pasta blends flour

Bulk Density of the Pasta blends flour samples was determined through following procedure. A sample (10g) was put in a calibrated 25 ml measuring cylinder and the initial volume was recorded. The bottom of the cylinder was tapped repeatedly on a firm pad on a laboratory bench until a constant volume was observed. Now, this volume in measuring cylinder was recorded as final volume. The bulk density was calculated as the ratio of the sample weight to the volume occupied by the sample before and after tapping (Pakhare et al., 2017).

Gluten content of pasta blend flour

For the evaluation of the Gluten content in pasta blend flour, 50 gram of flour was taken from each sample and dough was prepared by adding sufficient amount of water. Prepared dough was dipped in the water for an hour. Then each dough was washed in the running water to squeeze off the starch and fibre part. Washing was done until squeezed water runs clear. After

washing, excessive water was squeezed and dried in hot air oven at 100 °C for 1 hour. Weight of dried gluten was taken and gluten content was calculated by the following equation (AACC, 2008; Pedersen and Jørgensen, 2007).

$$\text{Gluten content \%} = \text{Weight of dry gluten (g)} / \text{Weight of flour (g)} \times 100$$

Swelling capacity (ml/g) of developed past

The swelling capacity of the developed pasta was determined by the method described by Okaka and Potter (Okaka and Potter, 1977). A graduated cylinder (100 ml) was filled with the sample up to 10 ml mark. The distilled water was added to give a total volume of 50 ml. The top of the graduated cylinder was tightly covered and mixed the flour and distilled water by inverting the cylinder. The suspension was inverted again after 2 min and left to stand for a further 8 min. After 8th min the volume occupied by the sample was recorded.

Cooking parameters of developed Pasta

Cooking properties is considered as the most important quality characteristics of pasta. Optimum Cooking time (OCT), swelling index and cooking loss / gruel loss are the parameters conducted as they express the cooking quality of Pasta products.

Optimum Cooking Time (OCT)

Optimum cooking time (minutes) for each developed pasta sample was determined according to the AACC (AACC, 2008). Pasta (10 g) was cooked in 100 ml of boiling distilled water and analysed every minute until it reached the optimum cooking time, considered as the time necessary to obtain complete gelatinisation of starch and it is shown by the disappearance of the white central core, after having pressed the pasta strand between two transparent glass slides (Brennan et al., 2004; Delcour et al., 2000; Edwards et al., 1993; Tudorica et al., 2002).

Swelling Index of cooked pasta

Swelling index of cooked pasta was measured by using the method described by Tudorica (Tudorica et al., 2002). Swelling Index of cooked pasta (SI; grams of water per gram of dry pasta) was evaluated by drying pasta samples to constant weight at 105 °C, expressed as:

$$\text{Swelling Index} = [\text{Weight of cooked product (W1)} - \text{Weight after drying (W2)}] / \text{Weight after drying (W2)}$$

Cooking Loss in cooked pasta

Cooking loss/ Solid Gruel in the cooking water collected from each sample was determined by evaporation to constant weight in a hot air oven at 103°C. The dried residue was weighed and calculated according to the following expression (AACC, 2008; Brennan et al. 2004; Bui and Small, 2007; Edwards et al. 1993).

$$\text{Cooking Loss} = [\text{Weight of cooking water dried residue} / \text{Weight of raw pasta}] \times 100$$

Chemical Characteristics

The chemical composition/ proximate composition analysis includes the estimation of moisture, ash, crude fat, crude protein, crude fibre, carbohydrate and energy value. This analysis was carried out by using following methods (Table 1). Determination of Moisture, ash and crude fibre content were determined according to AOAC methods. Protein content was determined as per

Kjeldhal Method. Crude fat content was determined by using Ether soxhlet Method. (Farzana and Mohajan, 2015; Sultana, 2020). Carbohydrate content of the pasta sample has been (nitrogen free extract or NFE) determined by the difference; that is, the sum of all the percentages of moisture, fat, crude protein, ash, and crude fiber was subtracted from 100%. This calculation provided the amount of nitrogen-free extract, otherwise known as carbohydrate and energy value of the sample was calculated using the “Atwater factor” by multiplying the values of the crude protein, lipid and carbohydrate by 3.99, 9.1, 3.99, respectively, and taking the sum of the product (Onwuk, 2005).

Table 1: Properties/ parameters of chemical analysis

Parameter	Description	References
Moisture Content (MC)	$MC (\%) = \frac{a - b}{c} \times 100$ Where: a = sample weight + crucible weight (before heating) (g) b = dry sample weight + crucible weight (after heating) (g) c = weight of sample (g)	(AOAC, 2000; Sultana, 2020)
Ash (A)	$A (\%) = \frac{\text{Weight of ash (g)}}{\text{Weight of sample (g)}} \times 100$	(AOAC, 2000)
Crude Protein (CP)	$CP (\%) = \% \text{ nitrogen} \times 6.25$	(AOAC, 2000; Farzana and Mohajan, 2015)
Crude Fat (CF)	$CF (\%) = \frac{\text{Weight of Fat}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$	(AOAC, 2000)
Crude Fibre (CFb)	$CFb (\%) = \frac{W1 - W2}{W} \times 100$ Where: W = weight of sample W1 = sample weight + crucible weight (before heating) W2 = dry sample weight + crucible weight (after heating)	(AOAC, 2000; Farzana and Mohajan, 2015)
Carbohydrate (C)	$C (\%) = 100 - [\text{moisture\%} + \text{fat (\%)} + \text{ash\%} + \text{crude fibre\%} + \text{crude protein\%}]$	(Onwuk, 2005)
Energy Value (E)	$E (\%) = [(\text{Crude Protein} \times 3.99) + (\text{Lipid} \times 9.1) + (\text{Carbohydrate} \times 3.99)]$	(Onwuk, 2005)

Statistical Analysis

Three independent observations of each sample for each test were taken and mean of these observations was used for statistical analysis *i.e.*, the calculation of SD and p-value and the data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The characteristics of pasta products, such as color, flavour, texture, taste and cooking properties are important factors which affect the consumer acceptance and product quality (Lee et al., 2002).

Prepared Pasta in different combinations

In this study, pasta (DWS 100%) alone and with different combination of DWS: RWF (90:10, 80: 20, 70: 30 & 60: 40%) were prepared. Fig. 1 shows the developed pasta samples with different treatments/ combinations.

Fig. 1: Pasta prepare in different combinations of DWS and RWF (A) DWS (100%); (B) DWS: RWF (90:10); (C) DWS: RWF (80:20) (D) DWS: RWF (70:30) & (E) DWS: RWF (60:40)

Sensory Analysis

The sensory evaluation of pasta is one of the most important factors in determining the consumer acceptance of pasta products. On the basis of sensorial performance its promotion and future commercialisation depends. It is one of the utmost significant parameters for assessing the quality of pasta products, which allows to evaluate the overall attributes of cooked pasta (Dick and Matsuo, 1988). Visual properties, such as colour or appearance, often influences the decision to buy a product by consumers (Duda et al., 2019; Sun-Waterhouse and Wadhwa, 2013). In this study, the sensory analysis of freshly cooked pasta in various combinations with control (DWS 100%) was carried out using 9 point hedonic scale with the help of a panel of 10 semi-trained evaluator. The pasta samples were evaluated separately for the sensory parameters like colour, flavour, texture, taste and overall acceptability by the each panellist. The effect on sensory parameters is presented in table 2. The observations indicated that the sensory parameters for all the treatment groups were scored positively ranges 7 to 8 score in total average of all attributes and may suggesting a good acceptance of DWS: RWF ratio of 70:30% by the panellists (Fig. 2) as compared to other observations/ ratio. Taken together these observations shows that the pasta prepared with DWS: RWF (70:30) resulted the most acceptable combination.

Table 2: Sensory attribute scores of developed pasta

Treatment	Colour	Flavour	Texture	Taste	Overall Acceptability (OAA)
DWS:RWF (100:00)	8	7.5	7	7	7
DWS:RWF (90:10)	8	7.5	7	7	7
DWS:RWF (80:20)	8	7.5	7.5	8	7.5
DWS:RWF (70:30)	8	8	8.5	8	8
DWS:RWF (60:40)	7.5	7	8.5	8	7

Values are Mean (± 1 SD) of three observations from independent.

Fig. 2: Sensory analysis of developed Pasta

Physical properties of Blends flour of DWS: RWF (70:30)

Physico-chemical characteristics of pasta is an important criteria for the final selection of sample. Physical properties were analysed and values were observed in all treatments. Blends flour of best pasta DWS: RWF (70:30) was studied for physical parameters such as bulk density, swelling capacity, gluten content and were observed 0.73, 3.0, and 10.29 respectively (Table 3).

Table 3: Physical properties of blends flour of best accepted ratio of developed pasta DWS (70%) and RWF (30%)

Physical properties	Blends flour of DWS:RWF (70:30)
Bulk density (gm/ml)	0.73±0.04
Swelling capacity (ml/gm)	3.0± 0.0
Gluten content %	10.29± 0.63

Chemical properties of developed pasta

Chemical properties such as crude protein, crude fat, fibre, ash, moisture, carbohydrate and energy are important characteristics of any food products. In present study these characteristics were evaluated. Developed Pasta in combination of DWS: RWF (70:30) were studied for their chemical properties *i.e.*, protein, fat, fibre, ash, moisture, carbohydrate and energy value and observed values were found 12.37%, 1.47%, 0.38%, 0.78%, 10.4%, 74.59 % and 360 Kcal/gm respectively. In previous studies

Pasta samples were prepared with DWS alone (100%) & for protein, fat, fibre, ash, moisture, carbohydrate and energy value (Kcal/gm), the reported data (Kamble et al., 2019) were used in this study as a reference to compare with best selected combination of developed pasta i.e. DWS: RWF (70:30) Table 4.

Table 4: Chemical properties of developed pasta sample DWS: RWF (70:30) in comparison with previously developed pasta DWS (100%)

Chemical properties	Pasta sample DWS (100)*	Pasta sample (DWS:RWF (70:30))
Protein (%)	12.30	12.37±0.99
Fat (%)	0.32	1.47±0.11
Fiber (%)	1.55	0.38±0.03
Ash (%)	0.47	0.78±0.03
Moisture (%)	7.01	10.4±0.63
Carbohydrate (%)	79.88	74.59±1.33
Energy (Kcal/gm)	371.66	360.39±3.16

*(Kamble et al., 2019)

As per results, its might concluded that pasta with DWS: RWF (70: 30) combination have slight improvement in terms of protein, fat and ash content as compared to DWS alone.

Cooking parameters of developed pasta

Cooking parameters plays a very important role in the consumer acceptance of pasta products. The most significant pasta quality factor is cooking quality. Cooking quality is based on a number of factors, including cooking duration, cooking loss, water absorption index, swelling index, and texture. Cooking nature and cooking parameters of pasta generally influenced by raw materials used in any preparation (Nilusha et al., 2019). In present study, best ratio of DWS: RWF *i.e.*, 70:30 were studied for Optimum Cooking Time (OCT), swelling index and gruel loss. OCT of DWS: RWF (70:30) was observed 7 min, whereas Swelling Index was found 1.56 (Table 5). One of the most significant factors influencing customer approval of pasta products is cooking loss (Fu, 2008; Rakhesh et al., 2015). As a result, it is widely employed as a predictor of the overall cooking performance of pasta. Cooking loss/ gruel loss was measured as the weight of total solids lost during cooking, and it was observed 2.77%, which is within the typical range (7-8%) for pasta from durum wheat (Dick and Matsuo, 1988).

Table 5: Cooking quality parameters of developed pasta sample

Cooking quality parameters	Pasta sample DWS:RWF (70:30)
Optimum Cooking Time (Min.)	7.0±0
Swelling Index	1.56±0.11
Gruel Loss (%)	2.77±0.46

CONCLUSION

Pasta Samples were prepared with Durum Wheat Semolina alone and in-combinations with increasing levels of Refined Wheat Flour *i.e.*, 10, 20, 30 and 40% and then analysed for their sensory parameters. Combination of Durum wheat semolina and Refined wheat flour with best consumer acceptability was selected which is DWS: RWF (70:30) and used for further studied such as their physico-chemical properties and cooking quality parameters. Findings of present study clearly depicted that Pasta sample prepared with DWS: RWF might be better version in above tested aspects as well as healthy, economical/ cost effective and easy to available. This combination might be used as basic formulation. So here we can conclude that little amendment in conventional ingredients of pasta can be improve developed pasta in number of ways. Mainly it can reduce the whole sole dependency on Durum wheat semolina.

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